

Unchain the code: how to ease quality control in research, tips or requirements?

Antonio F. Di Narzo^{†1} and Simona Rossi* ^{†2}

¹Mount Sinai School of Medicine, Department of Genetics and Genomic Sciences, Institute of Genomics and Multiscale Biology, One Gustave L. Levy Place – Box 1498, New York, NY 10029-6574, USA²SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, Quartier Sorge - Bâtiment Génopode, 1015, Lausanne, Switzerland

Email: Simona Rossi* - simona.rossi@unil.ch

* Corresponding author † Contributed equally

Biohelikon: Computational Biology 2012, 1(1):

<http://biohelikon.org>

© 2012 by Biohelikon

[Unchain the code: how to ease quality control in research, tips or requirements?](#) [Abstract](#) [The Key Rules](#) [Key Benefits](#) [Some Tips for Writing](#) [Redistributable Code](#) [Conclusion](#) [References](#)

Unchain the code: how to ease quality control in research, tips or requirements?

[Return to top](#)

Abstract

The importance of responsible conduct in research is well understood, and is rightfully receiving increasing attention in the last years, both from the scientific community itself [1,2] and from governmental agencies, which found research based on scientific production, which is mainly measured by the amount and quality of published papers [3,4].

[Return to top](#)

The Key Rules

Responsible conduct in research encompasses several aspect of the research practice. However, one of its key points is the need of transparency and reproducibility of the research procedures.

In a wet laboratory context, delivering transparent and reproducible results requires considerable efforts from the involved actors, and is usually not limited to careful writing of the materials and methods in the submitted manuscript, but includes the redaction of day-by-day well sorted laboratory notebooks.

But what about in silico experiments and data analysis procedures, which are the backbones of bioinformatics?

As it turns out, in silico procedures have a great advantage over their wet laboratory counterparts: they are executed by machines (the computers) which pedantly follow instructions (the computer code) which are written down and re-used by the bioinformaticians. Keeping for a moment aside problems linked to the use of live resources (e.g., external databases), we can be confident that a computer which is executing a same code twice, will produce twice the exact same results.

Bioinformaticians thus have the possibility to aim for a standard which is rather ideal in the wet laboratory context: they can target 100% reproducibility of their results. But the advantages are not limited to 100% reproducibility: by writing down the code which is needed to perform the required analyses, bioinformaticians get for free the equivalent of the laboratory notebook which would have required dedicate effort in a wet laboratory and in any case, naturally prone to human errors.

This advantage, however, is often overlooked. The code which was used to obtain published results is often just not available.

Given the current wide availability of public, free and reliable code repositories [5], there is really no excuse for not providing the code together with a manuscript.

Motivations behind authors unwillingness to share code are often laughable:

- a) 'Code stealing' is a no go for an excuse: if you want to publish on a scientific journal, you need to open up all the details of what you did anyway. In case the author's intention is to sell the software, then other channels should and might be used (i.e., canonical advertising).
- b) If the reason for not providing the code is that the code is 'not ready yet for prime time', i.e. the authors would like to clean it up before public

disclosure, then perhaps the manuscript submission itself should be postponed until the code is actually ready to be shared.

In all cases, a well written methods section is no substitute for the codes. While the methods section is prose, the codes are precise schematic instructions which, while hopefully readable by both humans and computers, leave no room to personal interpretations. As such, the codes always constitute the ultimate truth about a data analysis procedure.

Special attention should then be given to papers which propose substantial new methodology, which could be potentially re-applied in other context and with other data. In these cases, code sharing is not only an obvious requirement for a scientific paper, but is also a moral obligation from the authors towards the scientific community.

In particular, authors should try to make the code easy to run by independent researchers. By easy to run, we mean with reasonable effort. A good practice is providing at least one minimal example from simulated data, so that potential users can quickly get started with it.

[Return to top](#)

Key Benefits

Providing reusable software together with a paper has a number of benefits, for both the scientific community as a whole, and for the original paper authors. First, the presence of reusable software encourages detailed scrutiny of the method by peer scientists. Second, it facilitates competition: having a readily available implementation for a certain method, greatly facilitates the development of alternative procedures, as benchmarking becomes more accessible. Third, it encourages actual usage of the method by a broader community of non-specialists, in that the potential users do not have to delve into the implementation details before actually using the new method. Wider usage brings in turn more visibility to the original authors and their respective institutions, improving reputation and, eventually, chances for further research funding.

[Return to top](#)

Some Tips for Writing Redistributable Code

As D. E. Knuth once wrote [6] :

“The best programs are written so that computing machines can perform them quickly and so that human beings can understand them clearly.”

Programming is not a trivial task, and writing good code is an art. But while writing good code can be a difficult task (not much different from writing good prose), there are simple guidelines which the scientist can follow to smooth the passage from in house, personal use only scripts, to widely redistributable code.

a) Think about redistribution as early as possible:

While developing the new method, try to split it in small, self contained components, which might be easier to assemble into a reusable software once the method and data analysis pipeline are refined.

b) Focus on the essentials of your method:

For instance, keep the data pre- and post-processing code separate; try to confine accidental technicalities away, so that external readers are not unnecessarily distracted by them.

c) If you know some R, wrap your code into an R package:

By putting your method into an R package, you get data manipulation, pre-post processing, and plotting capabilities, all for free. You can still write core functionality in your language of choice. C/C++ and Fortran codes are particularly easy to embed in your R package, as R itself is written mainly in C and Fortran. R comes also with Java support built in. Finally, external binaries can be bundled with your package, and written in pretty much an arbitrary programming language.

The Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN, <http://cran.r-project.org/>) has plenty of examples of packages which wrap functionalities written in other programming languages. As a great example of code redistribution via R packaging, we recommend the more statistically inclined readers to study the recent work of Friedman et al. (2010) [7] . Their software is fast, reliable, has great documentation, and is exceptionally easy to redistribute.

[Return to top](#)

Conclusion

Paper authors should provide the code with which the research was conducted.

When the manuscript introduces substantially novel methodology, it should ideally include an easy to use, self-contained software. This not only helps the scientific community as a whole, but improves the visibility and reputation of the original authors and their research groups.

When the authors lack the means to build such a software, there is still no excuse for not making an effort to provide detailed documentation for all the code, so that an independent researcher can reproduce the published results with reasonable effort.

Furthermore, when bioinformatics or data analysis in general lead to the discovery of genomic signatures that will ultimately be applied in clinical trials and therefore patients, sharing documented code along with the methods to well support the published results should be required for at least two reasons: easier external validation phase, possible detection of errors avoiding the possibility to put patients in danger [8] .

Acknowledgments

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement N° 270089.

References

1. Fang FC, Steen RG, Casadevall A: **Misconduct accounts for the majority of retracted scientific publications.** [\[http://www.pnas.org/content/early/2012/09/27/1212247109\]](http://www.pnas.org/content/early/2012/09/27/1212247109) *PNAS[Internet]* 2012.
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)
2. Martinson BC, Anderson MS, Vries RD: **Scientists behaving badly.** *Nature* 2005, **435**:737-738.
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)
3. [\[http://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/not93-177.html\]](http://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/not93-177.html)
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)
4. [\[http://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-11-084.html\]](http://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-11-084.html)
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)
5. [\[http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Comparison_of_selected_papers_on_computer_science_of_open_source_software_hosting_facilities\]](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Comparison_of_selected_papers_on_computer_science_of_open_source_software_hosting_facilities)
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)
6. Donald EK: **Selected papers on computer science.** *Cambridge University Press, New York, NY, USA* 1996.
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)
7. Friedman J, Hastie T, Tibshirani R: **Regularization Paths for Generalized Linear Models via Coordinate Descent.** *J Stat Softw* 2010, **33**:1-22.
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)
8. Baggerly KA, Coombes KR: **What information should be required to support clinical "omics" publications?** *Clin Chem* 2011, 688-690.
Return to citation in text: [\[1\]](#)